

**The Impact of Adolescent Vaping Exposure on the Development of Respiratory Illnesses in
Early Adulthood: A Prospective Cohort Study**

Josef Hodgkins, MTS, BSN, RN, PhD Student

Florida State University, College of Nursing, Tallahassee FL, USA

September 5, 2025

Abstract

Background: Adolescent use of electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS), or vaping devices, has increased substantially, fueled by misperceptions of safety compared to traditional cigarettes. Although acute harms such as e-cigarette or vaping product use-associated lung injury (EVALI) are documented, the long-term respiratory outcomes of adolescent vaping remain poorly understood.

Methods: This prospective cohort study will recruit 2,000 adolescents (ages 13–17) from three U.S. states with high vaping prevalence and follow them for 10 years. Vaping exposure will be assessed through validated self-report surveys, salivary cotinine analysis, and environmental monitoring of secondhand aerosol exposure. Respiratory outcomes include physician-diagnosed illness (e.g., asthma, chronic bronchitis, EVALI) and spirometry-based measures of pulmonary function, verified through electronic health records and standardized clinical evaluations.

Multivariable Cox proportional hazards models will evaluate associations between vaping and incident respiratory disease, adjusting for confounders such as socioeconomic status, tobacco use, and environmental factors.

Results: This design enables assessment of temporality, dose-response, and cumulative effects of vaping on respiratory health, while minimizing recall and selection bias.

Conclusions: Findings will generate critical evidence on the long-term impact of adolescent vaping, supporting nursing-led prevention, clinical screening, and policy initiatives to mitigate youth vaping-related harm.

Keywords: adolescent vaping, electronic nicotine delivery systems, respiratory illness, cohort study, nursing research

Introduction & Rationale

Electronic nicotine delivery systems (ENDS), commonly known as vaping devices, have seen a sharp rise in use among adolescents and young adults, driven in part by the widespread but inaccurate perception that they are a safer alternative to traditional cigarettes (Kim, 2025). Emerging evidence implicates vaping in serious respiratory illnesses, most notably e-cigarette or vaping product use-associated lung injury (EVALI), with additional reports suggesting links to conditions such as lipoid pneumonia, chronic bronchitis, and asthma-related complications (Kalininskiy et al., 2019). Although regulatory measures have increased, critical gaps remain in understanding the long-term cardiopulmonary effects of adolescent vaping, due to limited longitudinal data and the evolving nature of ENDS products (Wold et al., 2022). There is growing concern about the inhalation of vape aerosols containing harmful substances, such as metals, volatile compounds, and flavoring agents, and their potential to cause acute and possibly long-term pulmonary inflammation, especially as e-cigarette use rises among adolescents (Kalininskiy et al., 2019). This study is highly relevant for nursing practice, as nurses are often at the frontline of health education, prevention, and chronic disease management. This research addresses a critical gap by investigating the long-term respiratory outcomes of adolescent vaping, providing evidence needed to inform preventative strategies in clinical and community health settings. The research question guiding this study is: "Does exposure to vaping during adolescence increase the risk of developing respiratory illness by early adulthood?" The central hypothesis is that adolescents who vape regularly demonstrate a significantly higher incidence of chronic respiratory conditions by age 25 compared to non-vaping peers.

Study Design

A prospective cohort study design is proposed to investigate the temporal relationship between adolescent vaping and the onset of respiratory illness in early adulthood. Prospective cohort studies enable researchers to define and measure exposures before disease onset, allowing for more accurate data collection and supporting stronger inferences about potential causal relationships (Andrade, 2022). Participants will be recruited during adolescence (ages 13–17) and followed for a period of 10 years, with annual assessments. This approach facilitates the classification of prospective exposure and the observation of incident respiratory outcomes. A key advantage of prospective designs is their ability to establish temporality and reduce recall bias, which is particularly important when studying substance use behaviors, such as vaping, that are often underreported in retrospective studies (Hajat et al., 2021). While cohort studies offer methodological strengths, they are often limited by high financial costs and the risk of participant attrition over extended follow-up, particularly when younger populations are involved (Stewart et al., 2021). Although resource-intensive, the ethical feasibility and substantial public health importance of studying vaping support ongoing longitudinal research to evaluate its long-term health effects (Vu et al., 2024).

Population and Sampling

The target population consists of adolescents aged 13–17 residing in urban and suburban school districts across three U.S. states with high vaping prevalence. The source population includes students enrolled in middle and high schools within these regions. Participants will be recruited using a demographically informed sampling strategy designed to ensure representation across socioeconomic and racial/ethnic groups, which are known to influence both vaping behaviors and respiratory health outcomes (Felner et al., 2022). Inclusion criteria include being

13–17 years old at baseline, obtaining informed consent from legal guardians, and being able to communicate in English or Spanish. Exclusion criteria include a prior diagnosis of chronic respiratory disease at baseline (e.g., asthma, cystic fibrosis) to allow for the measurement of incident outcomes. Recruitment will be conducted through school-based health centers and public health campaigns, with incentives provided to enhance enrollment and retention. Longterm follow-up will be supported by periodic digital engagement (e.g., text message reminders, app-based surveys). Sample size considerations include anticipated vaping prevalence (~25%), estimated respiratory outcome incidence (10–15%), and a 20% attrition rate over 10 years; the final sample will require at least 2,000 participants to ensure statistical power. Retention efforts will include school-based partnerships, regular participant contact through digital reminders and newsletters, and modest incentives tied to study milestones, consistent with best practices for adolescent longitudinal cohorts.

Exposure Measurement

Vaping exposure will be assessed using a multi-method approach. Self-reported data will be collected via validated surveys (e.g., Youth Tobacco Survey items) (Gentzke, 2022), capturing frequency, duration, and type of vaping products used (nicotine vs. THC-containing). To enhance measurement validity, salivary biospecimens are collected to enable biochemical verification of nicotine exposure through cotinine analysis (Thrul et al., 2023). Environmental exposure to vaping, particularly through household and peer use, is increasingly recognized as a source of secondhand aerosol exposure with potential health implications (Amalia et al., 2023). Environmental exposure to vaping will be captured through newly created household and peer usage surveys, recognizing the influence of secondhand aerosol exposure. For a subset of participants, wearable personal aerosol monitors will be used to assess acute exposure episodes.

Wearable personal exposure monitors capable of measuring fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) have been used to identify acute exposure episodes potentially related to e-cigarette use, demonstrating the feasibility of assessing vaping-related aerosol exposure in real time (Bernasconi et al., 2025). The combination of subjective and objective data strongly increases validity and reliability. Periodic recalibration of measurement tools and consistency checks across waves will ensure the precision of the results. Pilot testing of instruments and training of data collectors will also mitigate information bias. Geographic information systems (GIS) mapping will be used to evaluate vape shop density in participant neighborhoods, offering environmental context for interpreting individual vaping behaviors and potential exposure risk (Askwith, 2022). Geospatial analysis will be conducted using ArcGIS Pro (Esri), while cotinine assays will follow CDC-recommended protocols for salivary nicotine biomarker validation.

Outcome Measurement

The primary outcome is the incidence of physician-diagnosed respiratory illness by age 25, including but not limited to chronic bronchitis, asthma, and EVALI. Diagnosis will be verified through electronic health record (EHR) access and self-report, with medical record abstraction conducted by trained nurses. Secondary outcomes include spirometry-based measures of pulmonary function (FEV₁, FVC), collected biennially. Spirometry-based measures such as FEV₁ and FVC are emphasized as key, reproducible indicators in the interpretation of pulmonary function, providing objective insights into respiratory health when integrated with clinical and pathophysiologic data (Lopes, 2025). Reliability will be ensured via standardized spirometry protocols and calibration of equipment. Participants who report respiratory symptoms without a clinical diagnosis will undergo a follow-up clinical evaluation to reduce outcome misclassification.

Confounding and Bias

Important confounders include prior tobacco use, socioeconomic factors, and environmental exposures, all of which have been associated with both e-cigarette use and respiratory health outcomes (Snell et al., 2025). In the design phase, stratification by SES and baseline environmental exposure will be applied. Multivariable regression models will adjust for these and other potential confounders (e.g., physical activity, pre-existing conditions). Matching is not employed to preserve generalizability. Selection bias was addressed through school-based recruitment and the use of sampling weights to adjust for differential enrollment and response rates. To reduce recall bias in self-reported vaping behaviors, the study employed repeated assessments and biochemical verification through salivary cotinine analysis (Coleman, 2023). To address attrition bias, a common issue in longitudinal research, multiple imputation will be employed to statistically manage missing data, in conjunction with study design strategies aimed at maximizing participant retention (Woods et al., 2024).

Ethical Considerations

The protocol will be approved by the Florida State University IRB, with youth assent and parental consent procedures aligned with NIH adolescent research guidelines. The study will adhere to ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice. Informed consent will be obtained from legal guardians, with assent from adolescents at enrollment and re-consent upon reaching adulthood. Privacy and data security will be ensured through the use of encrypted databases, de-identification, and restricted access protocols. Given the involvement of minors and sensitive behavioral data, a Certificate of Confidentiality will be obtained. Risks to participants include psychological distress from medical evaluations and breach of confidentiality; these will be minimized by offering counseling resources and secure data

handling. Benefits include health screenings and educational materials on the harms of vaping. The study promotes environmental justice by including diverse populations and sharing results with affected communities through accessible channels.

Data Analysis Plan

Descriptive statistics will be used to characterize the cohort at baseline. Cox proportional hazards models will assess the association between adolescent vaping and time to respiratory diagnosis, adjusting for confounders (Cox, 1972). Subgroup analyses will explore dose-response and peer/family exposure effects. The study's prospective design, repeated measures of exposure and outcomes, and subgroup dose-response analysis enable assessment of temporal relationships and exposure gradients critical to causal inference. For secondary outcomes, generalized estimating equations (GEE) will be used to evaluate changes in pulmonary function over time (Liang & Zeger, 1986). Spatial analysis will examine the clustering of vape shops and their outcomes (Cromley & McLafferty, 2011).

Dissemination and Implications for Nursing

Findings will be disseminated through peer-reviewed journals, nursing and public health conferences, and community health briefs shared with participating schools and local health departments. Dissemination will follow the principles of knowledge translation, using the REAIM framework to guide reporting on reach, adoption, implementation, and maintenance potential in school and public health settings. Results will directly inform clinical screening practices, school-based education, and policy advocacy for youth vaping regulation. Advanced practice nurses can apply this evidence in anticipatory guidance, early identification of at-risk youth, and community health interventions. The study supports nursing research leadership in

addressing emerging environmental health risks and promoting respiratory health equity across the lifespan.

References

- Amalia, B., Fu, M., Tigova, O., Ballbè, M., Paniello-Castillo, B., Castellano, Y., ... & TackSHS Project Investigators. (2023). Exposure to secondhand aerosol from electronic cigarettes at homes: A real-life study in four European countries. *Science of The Total Environment*, 854, 158668.
- Andrade, C. (2022). Research design: cohort studies. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine*, 44(2), 189-191.
- Askwith, Z. O. (2022). *Environmental Influences on E-cigarette Use Among Young People* (Master's thesis, The University of Western Ontario (Canada)).
- Bernasconi, S., Angelucci, A., Rossi, A., & Aliverti, A. (2025). A New Wearable System for Personal Air Pollution Exposure Estimation: Pilot Observational Study. *JMIR mHealth and uHealth*, 13, e60426.
- Coleman, A. (2023). *Adolescent Electronic Cigarette Screening: A Quality Improvement Project*. University of Louisiana at Lafayette.
- Cox, D. R. (1972). Regression models and life-tables. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society: Series B (Methodological)*, 34(2), 187–202.
- Cromley, E. K., & McLafferty, S. L. (2011). *GIS and public health* (2nd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Felner, J. K., Andrzejewski, J., Strong, D., Kieu, T., Ravindran, M., & Corliss, H. L. (2022). Vaping disparities at the intersection of gender identity and race/ethnicity in a populationbased sample of adolescents. *Nicotine and Tobacco Research*, 24(3), 349-357.
- Gentzke, A. S. (2022). Tobacco product use and associated factors among middle and high school students—National Youth Tobacco Survey, United States, 2021. *MMWR. Surveillance Summaries*, 71.

- Hajat, C., Selya, A., & Stein, E. (2021). Critical analysis of common methodology flaws in ecigarette surveys. *Qeios*.
- Kalininskiy, A., Bach, C. T., Nacca, N. E., Ginsberg, G., Marraffa, J., Navarette, K. A., ... & Croft, D. P. (2019). E-cigarette, or vaping, product use associated lung injury (EVALI): case series and diagnostic approach. *The Lancet Respiratory Medicine*, 7(12), 1017-1026.
- Kim, J. (2025). *Case Study Describing Alumni's Perceptions of High School Interventions for Electronic Nicotine Delivery Systems (ENDS)* (Doctoral dissertation, Youngstown State University).
- Liang, K. Y., & Zeger, S. L. (1986). Longitudinal data analysis using generalized linear models. *Biometrika*, 73(1), 13–22.
- Lopes, A. J. (2025). Pulmonary function tests: an integrated approach to interpreting results in the search for treatable traits. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*, 19(2), 121-143.
- Snell, L. M., Barnes, A. J., & Eissenberg, T. (2025). Variation in Relative Risk Perceptions and Tobacco Use by Race and Socioeconomic Status Among Older Adults Who Smoke: Evidence From the Population Assessment of Tobacco and Health Study. *Nicotine and Tobacco Research*, 27(7), 1168-1176.
- Stewart, A. C., Cossar, R., Walker, S., Wilkinson, A. L., Quinn, B., Dietze, P., ... & Stoové, M. (2021). Strategies to maximise study retention and limit attrition bias in a prospective cohort study of men reporting a history of injecting drug use released from prison: the prison and transition health study. *BMC medical research methodology*, 21(1), 185.
- Thrul, J., Howe, C. L., Devkota, J., Alexander, A., Allen, A. M., Businelle, M. S., ... & Gordon, J. S. (2023). A scoping review and meta-analysis of the use of remote biochemical verification methods of smoking status in tobacco research. *Nicotine and Tobacco Research*, 25(8), 1413-1423.

Vu, G. T., Stjepanović, D., Sun, T., Leung, J., Chung, J., Connor, J., ... & Chan, G. (2024).

Predicting the long-term effects of electronic cigarette use on population health: a systematic review of modelling studies. *Tobacco Control*, 33(6), 790-797.

Wold, L. E., Tarran, R., Crotty Alexander, L. E., Hamburg, N. M., Kheradmand, F., St. Helen, G.,

... & American Heart Association Council on Basic Cardiovascular Sciences; Council on Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis and Vascular Biology; Council on Hypertension; and Stroke

Council. (2022). Cardiopulmonary consequences of vaping in adolescents: a scientific statement

from the American Heart Association. *Circulation research*, 131(3), e70-e82. Woods, A. D.,

Gerasimova, D., Van Dusen, B., Nissen, J., Bainter, S., Uzdavines, A., ... & Elsherif, M. M.

(2024). Best practices for addressing missing data through multiple imputation. *Infant and Child*

Development, 33(1), e2407.